

1 **INHIBITORY EFFECT OF AZA-MACROCYCLIC LIGANDS ON POLYPHENOL OXIDASE IN**
2 **MODEL AND FOOD SYSTEMS.**

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12 **ABSTRACT**

13 Enzymatic browning is one of the main problems faced by the food industry due to the
14 enzyme polyphenol oxidase (PPO) action provoking undesirable colour change in the
15 presence of oxygen. Here, we report the evaluation of ten different azamacrocyclic
16 compounds with diverse morphologies as potential inhibitors against the activity of PPO,
17 both in model and real systems. An initial screening of ten ligands show that all aza-
18 macrocyclic compounds inhibit to some extent the enzymatic browning, but the
19 molecular structure plays a crucial role on the power of inhibition. Kinetic studies of the
20 most active ligand (L2) reveal a S-parabolic I-parabolic non-competitive inhibition
21 mechanism and a remarkable inhibition at micromolar concentration ($IC_{50} = 10 \mu M$).
22 Furthermore, L2 action has been proved on apple juice significantly reducing the
23 enzymatic browning.

24

25 **Key words:** PPO, inhibition, macrocyclic polyamines, enzymatic activity

26

27 **1. Introduction**

28 There is currently a growing tendency to consume fresh, cut, ready-to-eat fruits and
29 vegetables or minimally processed fresh juices as there is a great concern for
30 maintaining a healthy diet and preserve their sensory and nutritional properties.
31 Therefore, maintaining the stability of the product and ensuring the natural colour is
32 one of the main objectives of the food industry ^{1,2}.

33 The main cause of colour modification of fruits and vegetables can be associated to the
34 activity of enzyme polyphenol oxidase (PPO, EC 1.14.18.1 or EC 1.10.3.1). The PPO
35 catalyse the *o*-hydroxylation of monophenols into *ortho*-phenols and its posterior
36 oxidation to *o*-quinones followed by a non-enzymatic polymerization of reactive
37 quinones leading to the enzymatic browning of foods³. This reaction starts when the
38 PPO enzyme and the atmospheric oxygen meet, usually during cell disruptions of the
39 raw food in their harvesting, handling and post-harvest processing. The colour change,
40 yet it is a desirable process in some foods⁴, is inversely correlated with the acceptability
41 of fruit and vegetable products by the consumer⁵ which causes a considerable increase
42 in food waste economic losses^{6,7}.

43 Since the factors that most influence enzymatic browning are the concentration of both
44 the active enzyme and the phenolic compounds (plus the pH, the temperature and the
45 presence of oxygen)⁸ the processing of foods with high concentrations of PPO and
46 polyphenols leads to a high risk of enzymatic browning in this type of food. A clear
47 example would be the case of apple juices, which contain considerable amounts of
48 polyphenols and polyphenol oxidases linked to suspended particles⁹.

49 Food waste is a major humanitarian and environmental problem (Food and Agriculture
50 Organization of the United Nations, 2011)¹⁰ so it is not unexpected that food processing
51 industry has been using different methods to prevent the enzymatic browning based on
52 both physical and chemical treatments. Traditionally, one of the methods most used by
53 the industry has been the thermal treatment. But heat induces changes in taste, colour,
54 smell and nutritional properties due to the decomposition of volatile and
55 thermosensitive compounds, such as aromas, vitamins, carotenoids and
56 anthocyanins^{11,12}. Regarding chemical treatments, the use of acidifying agents, chelators
57 or sulphites have also been used as preventive for browning, but the fact that they can
58 interfere with the taste or even cause allergies in the population (sulphites) has
59 restricted their use in foods and beverages^{13,14}. These drawbacks encourage researchers
60 to still look for a novel strategies of PPO inhibitors, as could be the use of the
61 nanomaterial technology^{15,16}.

62 From another point of view, supramolecular chemistry is a research subject of great
63 interest at present. It studies the non-covalent interactions between molecules, usually
64 named host and guest. The host molecules, in general, are large molecules capable of
65 enclosing smaller molecules and they can be natural, semi-synthetic or completely
66 synthetic molecules. On the other hand, the smaller guest molecules can be cationic,
67 anionic or neutral like amino acids, organic anions and some metals¹⁷.

68 Within the receptors designed for supramolecular studies, macrocyclic polyamines are
69 especially relevant¹⁸. Polyamines offer a high potential as PPO inhibitors since these
70 compounds can interact with metal cations with biological relevance such as Cu^{+2} ¹⁹⁻²¹ and
71 have also the ability to interact with amino acids through hydrogen bonds or
72 electrostatic interactions. In addition, these ligands can be functionalized with different

73 chemical groups like aromatic groups or alkyl groups that can change their response over
74 the PPO.

75 So far there are no studies aimed at studying the interactions between this type of
76 compounds and polyphenol oxidase as a strategy for their inhibition in food systems.

77 We can hypothesize that azamacrocycles can interact with the copper atoms in the
78 active centre of the external part of the enzyme modifying its activity. Therefore, this
79 work aims at analyse the behaviour of different azamacrocyclic compounds in the
80 inhibition or modulation of the polyphenol oxidase enzyme activity in model and real
81 systems, as starting point to develop an alternative strategy for the industrial processing
82 of fruits and vegetables.

83 2. Materials and methods

84 2.1. Chemicals

85 Commercial mushroom tyrosinase enzyme (2687 U/mg), dopamine hydrochloride
86 ((HO)₂C₆H₃CH₂NH₂·HCL) and HEPES (C₈H₁₈N₂O₄S) were purchased all from Sigma-Aldrich
87 (Sigma-Aldrich, USA). For the buffers, sodium bisphosphate (NaH₂PO₄) and disodium
88 phosphate (Na₂HPO₄) were acquired from Scharlau (Sharlab S.L., Spain) and anhydrous
89 sodium acetate (NaCH₃COO) from Panreac AppliChem (Panreac AppliChem, Barcelona,
90 Spain).

91 The ligand S1 (cyclam) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Sigma-Aldrich, USA). The
92 others tested ligands were synthesised according to known procedures and the
93 characterisation agrees with published data: S2²², S3²³, S4²⁴, M1²⁵, M2²⁶, M3²⁷, L1²⁸, L2²⁹
94 and L3³⁰. The different chemical structures are summarized in Scheme 1.

95 The juices used in the tests were obtained in the laboratory by directly liquefying apples
96 (Golden Delicious variety, Val Venosta) obtained in a local store.

97

98 Scheme 1: Molecular structure of the ten studied azamacrocyclic ligand

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100 2.2. Screening of the best inhibitors over tyrosinase from mushroom

101 Polyphenol oxidase activity in the presence of the ligands was determined following the
 102 protocol published by Muñoz-Pina et al.(2020)¹⁶ and with some modifications from
 103 Siddiq and Dola (2017)³¹. Tyrosinase from mushroom (93.75 U) was put in contact with
 104 dopamine (2.5 mM) in presence of the ligand (0.67 mM) in a phosphate buffer 10 mM
 105 at pH 5.5. A control without inhibitor was used. The oxidation of the dopamine by the
 106 PPO produces an orange colour that is followed spectrophotometrically at 420 nm
 107 measuring the absorbance each 10 s during 10 min. As in the case of fruits and their

108 respective juices the typical pH found is between 3.5 and 5.5, to perform the assays it
109 was chosen pH=5.5, in which the PPO continued to have a high activity (around 85%)
110 but was similar to the pH found in fruit juices³². From the absorption-time curves, the
111 slope of the linear stretch is obtained, related to the initial speed of the reaction. The
112 different slopes were used to compare the inhibitory effect of the ligands against the
113 control (see equation 1). The reaction was followed by a Beckman Coulter DU-730 Life
114 Science UV/Vis spectrophotometer in triplicate at 24 °C. PPO inhibition was calculated
115 according to Eq. (1), where V_{00} is the control initial rate and V_{0i} is the initial rate obtained
116 for the different samples.

$$117 \text{ PPO inhibition (\%)} = 100 - \left(\frac{V_{0i}}{V_{00}} * 100 \right) \quad (1)$$

118 2.3. Enzyme-ligand interaction

119 To evaluate the influence of the contact time between the enzyme and the ligands, the
120 enzyme was put in contact with the ligand at time 0 min and at 60 min. The
121 azamacrocyclic compounds selected for the assay were M1, M2, M3, L2 and L3 (all at
122 0.67 mM). The reaction mixture was the same as in 2.2 and in both times a control
123 without inhibitor was prepared.

124 The absorbance was then measured at 420 nm every 10 s for 10 min in a Beckman
125 Coulter DU-730 Life Science UV/Vis spectrophotometer and the effect of the contact
126 time on the initial rate was compared. PPO inhibition was calculated according to Eq.
127 (1), where V_{00} is the control initial rate and V_{0i} is the initial rate obtained for the different
128 samples.

129 The oxygen consumption during the enzymatic catalysed oxidation was measured to
130 monitor the PPO activity. The oxygen concentration in solution was measured with a
131 Oxyview 1 measuring system of Hansatech Instruments, which contains a S1 Clark-type

132 polarographic oxygen electrode disc mounted within a DW1/AD electrode chamber and
133 connected to the Oxyview electrode control unit. The oxygen consumption vs time curve
134 was plotted and the initial rate of oxygen consumption measured from the positive slope
135 of the initial part. PPO inhibition was calculated then according to Eq. (1), where V_{00} is
136 the control positive initial rate of oxygen consumption and V_{0i} is the initial rate of oxygen
137 consumption obtained for the different samples.

138 2.4. Enzyme kinetics in model systems

139 The five compounds with more inhibitory capacity were chosen to make a deeper study
140 of enzymatic activity. For the determination of the kinetic parameters, the reaction was
141 carried out at pH 5.5 under phosphate buffer 10 mM at ten different concentrations of
142 the substrate dopamine (from 0.033 mM to 1.66 mM). The inhibitor/enzyme mixture
143 was subsequently added to start the enzymatic reaction. The final concentration of
144 enzyme in the assay was 93.75 U and the inhibitor concentration varied depending of
145 its response. A control without inhibitor was also carried out. The absorbance at 420 nm
146 was measured every 10 s for 10 min in a Spectrophotometer Beckman Coulter DU-730
147 Life Science UV / Vis Spectrophotometer. The production of dopamine was determined
148 using a molar extinction coefficient for dopachrome of $\epsilon = 3700 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ³³.

149 Since the enzymatic reaction of polyphenol oxidase follows a kinetics of Michaelis
150 Menten³⁴, K_M and v_{\max} constants were calculated using the Lineweaver-Burk
151 representation as a linearization method and compared to the representation of
152 Langmuir³⁵. The type of inhibition was also determined. Furthermore, the inhibition
153 constant (K_i) for an enzyme-ligand complex were analysed by Dixon plot, which is a
154 graphical method plot of $1/\text{enzyme velocity}$ ($1/V$) versus inhibitor concentration (I) with
155 varying concentrations of the substrate. For the determination of IC_{50} values, the

156 concentration of individual ligand to achieve 50% PPO inhibition were calculated.
157 Besides, GraphPad Prism 5.00.288 program was used to carry out various statistical
158 analyses such as the analysis of variance (ANOVA) of one factor and two factors,
159 depending on the case.

160 2.5. Fluorescence quenching analysis

161 The fluorescence assay was performed with a PTI fluorescence instrument. Same
162 inhibitor/enzyme mixture as in section 2.2. was used in this study at the three ligand
163 concentrations. Tyrosinase was excited at 274 nm and the emission spectrum over the
164 range of 280 nm to 400 nm was recorded through a 3 nm slit. The emission spectrum of
165 the tyrosinase solution was also directly measured.

166 2.6. Inhibitory effect over apple juice

167 Apple juice from cv. Golden Delicious obtained in the laboratory was selected to verify
168 their inhibitory effects of the compounds on real samples. For each compound, a 2 mL
169 aliquot of juice was put in contact with 2 mg and 4 mg of compound and another 2 mL
170 of apple juice was used as a control sample. All samples were kept under agitation (400
171 rpm) for 60 minutes and photographs were taken at 0, 1 and 2 minutes and then at 5-
172 minute intervals, in order to monitor and visualize the enzymatic browning.
173 Furthermore, CIE L*a*b* (CIELAB) coordinates were measured in the images and colour
174 differences were calculated using Adobe® Photoshop®.

175 2.7. Data analysis

176 Data are reported as mean \pm standard deviation. Origin was used to perform the analysis
177 of variance (One-Way ANOVA) and the LSD procedure (least significant difference).
178 Partial least squares regression studies (PLS) were carried out with the R 3.6.0 software
179 using the Kernel algorithm. Scale and center were used as parameters to build the

180 model. Leave one out (LOO) cross-validation was used to evaluate the adequacy of the
181 experimental data and to select the quantity of latent variables.

182 **3. Results and discussion**

183 3.1. Selection of the best inhibitors

184 A macrocyclic ligand can interact directly with enzymes via supramolecular interactions,
185 but at the same time, it is able to bind a metal atom within its central cavity. Besides,
186 this cavity can be branched or functionalized with other chemical groups to stimulate
187 the interactions with further species as enzymes²⁴. The size and spatial arrangement of
188 the coordinating groups are of great importance since it significantly influences the
189 properties of the complexes and this affects their selectivity³⁶. First on this study diverse
190 compounds with different chemical structures were chosen in order to evaluate the
191 effect of their presence in the oxidation reaction of dopamine by polyphenol oxidase
192 (see scheme 1). The selected compounds have in common a macrocyclic unit. The size
193 of the cavity varies depending of the number of atoms in the ring. Therefore, for clarity
194 in the discussion, the ligands were divided according to the number of nitrogen groups
195 in the macrocycle in small (S1, S2, S3, and S4), medium (M1, M2, and M3) and large (L1,
196 L2, and L3).

197 An initial screening of the inhibitory activity was accomplished measuring the
198 absorbance at 420 nm in presence of the ligand at pH 5.5 with dopamine as a substrate
199 (Figure 1). In general terms, all the ligands reduce the initial reaction rate, which can be
200 translated as a partial inhibition of the enzymatic activity. The degree of inhibition varies
201 strongly among the ligands with a decrease in the initial PPO rate from 11.4 to 94.5 %
202 depending on the chemical structure. %. On a first sight, it can be seen how smallest
203 cycles (S1, S2, S3, and S4) were not able to reduce the enzymatic activity of the PPO

204 more than 40%. Besides, M1, M2, and M3, bigger in structure, presented better
205 inhibition power with M3 inhibiting 70% the PPO activity. Finally, L2 induces the greatest
206 inhibition over the PPO (almost 95%) seeming that the functionalization with the two
207 naphth-2-ylmethyl plays an important role. However, not only the naphth-2-ylmethyl
208 units makes the difference as L3 present less inhibition (70%) having the same units but
209 with an amine between the macrocycle and the naphthalene.

210 If we compare these values with those reported by Wei Liu and co-workers³⁷ using citric
211 acid as a typical tyrosinase inhibitor we can observe that these ligands present higher
212 power of inhibition. In the case of citric acid, it was necessary a concentration superior
213 to 10 mM to reach an inhibition of the 20% over tyrosinase from mushroom. They also
214 report that the minimum of citric acid was 10 mM to strongly inhibit the PPO from
215 bananas. Even though this behaviour depends on the substrate source (catechol vs
216 dopamine), in our case all the ligands present 10 times superior inhibition power with
217 only 0.67 mM. Regarding to others commonly used organic acids, such as oxalic acid,
218 Son et al.,³⁸ pointed out that a concentration of approximately 1 mM could inhibit the
219 PPO in a 50% and 5 mM to reach the 80%. Similar behaviour is reported for benzoic
220 acid³⁹ over mushroom PPO where in needed a concentration of 5.20 mM to reach the
221 50% of inhibition. In our case most of the ligands from the M and L family reporter
222 greatest inhibitory force as they need less concentration than 1 mM to reach more than
223 the 50%.

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227 Figure 1: Polyphenol oxidase (94 U) inhibition in presence of the ten different
 228 azamacrocyclic ligand (0.67 mM) using dopamine as substrate (2.5 mM).

229

230 In order to gain insight about the influence of the chemical structure in the PPO activity,
 231 the ligands were parameterized (see table 1) and the degree of inhibition modeled
 232 with the Partial Least Squares Regression (PLS) technique. The PLS is a multivariate
 233 projection method that models the relation between an array of dependent variables
 234 (Y) and another array of independent variables (X) to find the components that allow
 235 the highest correlation with Y. In our case the independent variables were the
 236 parameterized data contained in the Table 1 and the dependent variable was the degree
 237 of inhibition shown in the Figure 1. All the data/ligands were included in the training set
 238 because the number of molecules was small, and we were interested in understanding
 239 the influence of the functional groups in the inhibitory activity measured during the
 240 screening.

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244 Table 1: Parameterized values of the ligands used in the PLS and squared values of the
 245 first four principal components.

Ligand / Loading	Ntot ^a	Pyr ^b	NH ^c	Nter ^d	Ant ^e	Amac ^f	OH ^g	Met ^h	Nmac ⁱ	Rsize ^j	Benz ^k	Sch ^l	Lch ^m	Inhib ⁿ
S1	4	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	4	14	0	0	0	11,4
S2	4	1	3	0	0	0	0	1	4	12	0	0	0	28,5
S3	4	1	3	0	0	0	1	0	4	12	0	0	0	19,7
S4	4	1	0	3	0	0	0	0	4	12	0	1	2	37,1
M1	5	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	5	20	1	0	0	54,4
M2	6	1	5	0	0	0	0	0	6	20	0	0	0	45,5
M3	7	1	6	0	0	0	0	0	7	24	0	0	0	71,4
L1	8	2	4	2	0	0	0	0	8	24	0	2	0	34,2
L2	8	2	4	2	2	2	0	0	8	24	0	0	2	94,5
L3	10	2	6	2	2	0	0	0	8	24	0	0	2	55,8
PC1 ⁺	0,1								0,08	0,77				
PC2 ⁺		0,05	0,52*	0,48	0,15	0,12				0,05*			0,45	
PC3 ⁺	0,16*	0,09*	0,19	0,29*					0,06*			0,16*		
PC4 ⁺	0,43*		0,61*		0,36*					0,21		0,26	0,13*	

246 ^a Ntot: total number of nitrogens. ^b Pyr: number of pyridine units. ^c NH: number of NH groups ^d Nter: number of
 247 tertiary amines ^e Ant: number of anthracene units ^f Amac: number of anthracene units attached to the macrocycle. ^g
 248 OH: number of OH groups. ^h Met: number of methoxy groups. ⁱ Nmac: number of N in the macrocycle. ^j Rsize: number
 249 of atoms that compose the macrocycle. ^k Benz: number of benzene units. ^l Sch: number of small chains attached to
 250 the macrocycle. ^m Lch: number of big chains attached to the macrocycle. ⁿ Inhib: % of inhibition calculated as 100-
 251 initial PPO rate. ⁺ Values lower than 0,05 have been omitted for clarity. * loadings with negative

252

253 To check the quality of the model the Leave One Out (LOO) method was used and 4
 254 latent variables selected. Figure 2 contains a graph with the measured vs. the predicted
 255 values of the inhibitory activity for each ligand. The measured and predicted values were
 256 plotted together to evaluate the accuracy and precision of the created prediction
 257 models. Ideally, the predicted values should lie along the diagonal line, indicating that
 258 the predicted and actual values are the same. As can be seen in Figure 2, in general a
 259 good fit is obtained and most of the points remain next to the solid line. Furthermore,
 260 a linear fitting of the by using of the points in the graph with a simple linear model ($y =$
 261 $ax + b$) offered values of 0.915, 3.86 and 0.915 for the slope, the intercept and R^2
 262 respectively.

263

264

265 Figure 2: Experimental versus predicted values by using a PLS statistical model (dashed
266 lines) for the PPO inhibition. The solid line represents ideal behaviour.

267

268 The effect of the chemical structure parameters defined in the table 1 in the inhibitory
269 activity, was analyzed from the squared loadings for the first four principal components
270 (PCs) (Table 1). In PLS the first principal component (PC1) contains the highest explained
271 variance and explains most of the inhibitory response, next PC2 and so on. In this case,
272 PC1 suggest that the ring size is the main factor responsible of the inhibitory response.
273 Also, high values are found for the total number of nitrogens (N_{tot}) and the number of
274 nitrogens in the macrocycle (N_{mac}), suggesting that together with the ring size, the
275 amino groups are highly relevant for the inhibitory activity. However, as the number of
276 nitrogen atoms in the ligand is high correlated with the macrocycle size, the inhibitory
277 effect can be assigned neither to the ring size nor to the total number of nitrogens
278 separately.

279 As can be seen in the table 1, we can assign as a second main factor in the ligands activity
280 (PC2) to the macrocycle functionalization (Nter, Ant, Amac), with preference for the big
281 size substituents (Lch) over the little groups (Sch). Also, the presence of the pyridine
282 moiety seems improve the response. Regarding the other two principal components,
283 the number of NH (PC3) and methyl groups (PC4) have a positive but minor effect. Other
284 functional groups such as the presence of benzene, the hydroxy or methoxy groups do
285 not seem offer any advantage.

286 From the structure of the ligands and the PLS analysis we can conclude that the key
287 factor of the inhibitory activity is the presence of a big macrocycle containing several
288 amino groups and it improves with the presence of bulky hydrophobic substituents (i.e.
289 i-Pr or anthracene) directly attached to the ring.

290 3.2. Ligand-PPO interaction

291 Since the ligands M1, M2, M3, L2, and L3 had reported the greatest power of inhibition
292 over the PPO (at least 50%), we selected them to analyse their interaction more
293 thoroughly.

294 As previously mentioned, the enzymatic browning process comprises two phases, firstly,
295 the enzymatically catalysed oxidation takes place, followed by a non-enzymatic
296 polymerization reaction that generates the brown colour⁴⁰. Although the appearance
297 of colour is generally used to follow the enzymatic browning reaction, the speed of
298 oxygen consumption allows us to prove that the effect of azamacrocyclic compounds is
299 directly related to the enzymatic activity (oxidation) and not associated with the non-
300 enzymatic polymerization of the quinones.

301

302

303 Figure 3: PPO (94 U) inhibition (%) based on colour formation (light grey) and based on
 304 oxygen consumption (dark grey) for the five selected ligands (0.67 mM).

305

306 As seen in figure 3, the initial rates of oxygen consumption and colour formation were
 307 compared for the five inhibitors selected. Despite being different methodologies, both
 308 techniques reveal an appreciable increase on the inhibition of the browning process.

309 The behaviour observed is that, although similar, the inhibition over the colour
 310 formation is higher than the inhibition of the oxygen consumption. This suggests that
 311 their mechanisms would not only involve with the enzyme, but an interfere with the
 312 polymerization reaction. By contrast, L2 shows a slight variance (5%) between both
 313 techniques and L3 does not show any meaningful difference between the initial velocity
 314 of oxygen consumption and colour formation. These results suggest that for L2 and L3
 315 the decrease in browning is mainly due to a decrease in the PPO activity.

316

317

318 Figure 4: Effect of contact time between polyphenol oxidase (94 U) and the different
 319 ligands on their inhibitory capacity prior to substrate addition. Without previous contact
 320 time (0 min; dark grey) and with 60 minutes of previous contact time (light grey).

321

322 Furthermore, the influence of the contact time between the enzyme and the different
 323 compounds should be considered as it might affect the inhibitory capacity over the PPO.

324 Thus, it was analysed the response of the five selected ligands varying the previous
 325 contact time between the ligand and the PPO prior to substrate addition (0 min and 60
 326 min). With the exception of M3 (see figure 4), the speed decreases as the contact time
 327 increases being the differences significant ($p < 0.0001$). This would indicate that if the
 328 enzyme and the inhibitor are previously in contact in solution, they are able to interact
 329 to a greater extent, obtaining higher inhibition values.

330 3.3. Kinetic parameters determination

331 As tyrosinase from mushroom follows Michaelis-Menten kinetics, in order to
 332 understand and compare the nature of the enzyme-inhibitor interaction, the classical

333 method of Lineweaver-Burk plots was used to determine the kinetic parameters and the
 334 inhibition mechanism for each inhibitor (see table 2). In the case of the Michaelis-
 335 Menten K_m constant, the value for the control was $K_M = 1.05 \pm 0.05$ mM and 0.3321
 336 mMmin^{-1} for v_{\max} .

337

338 Table 2: Kinetic parameters and type of inhibition of the enzyme Tyrosinase from
 339 mushroom (94 U) in presence of the five selected ligands at different concentrations.

Compound (mM)	K_M^a (mM)	v_{\max}^b (mM min ⁻¹)	k_{cat}^c (min ⁻¹)	Catalytic efficiency ^d (mM ⁻¹ min ⁻¹)	IC ₅₀ (mM)	K _i (mM)	Inhibition type	
Control	1.05 ± 0.05*	0.3324 ± 0.0108	1700 ± 50	1620 ± 140				
M1	0.67	1.01 ± 0.06*	0.091 ± 0.004 [†]	467 ± 19	460 ± 40	0.23 ± 0.02	0.28 ± 0.03	Non-competitive
	1.33	1.007 ± 0.118*	0.03 ± 0.002 [§]	160 ± 10	160 ± 30			
M2	0.67	1.01 ± 0.03*	0.099 ± 0.002 [†]	510 ± 10	500 ± 20	0.25 ± 0.04	0.28 ± 0.02	Non-competitive
	1.33	1.02 ± 0.05*	0.0587 ± 0.0016 [§]	303 ± 8	300 ± 20			
M3	0.1	0.71 ± 0.05	0.119 ± 0.005	610 ± 20	860 ± 80	0.09 ± 0.03	0.133 ± 0.009	Mixed type
	0.33	0.73 ± 0.03	0.073 ± 0.002 [†]	377 ± 14	520 ± 40			
L3	0.1	1.08 ± 0.05*	0.032 ± 0.002 [§]	164 ± 5	150 ± 10	0.022 ± 0.007	0.027 ± 0.008	Non-competitive
	0.67	0.97 ± 0.17*	0.02 ± 0.002	100 ± 10	100 ± 30			
L2	0.005	1.08 ± 0.14*	0.29 ± 0.04	1490 ± 190	1380 ± 50	0.010 ± 0.002	0.015 ± 0.003 ^e	Non-competitive
	0.01	1.011 ± 0.014*	0.162 ± 0.005	840 ± 30	830 ± 20			
	0.04	1.2 ± 0.2*	0.038 ± 0.008 [§]	200 ± 40	167 ± 4			

340 ^a Michaelis-Menten constant, dependent of enzyme concentration. ^b Reaction rate, dependent on enzyme
 341 concentration. ^c Catalytic constant, $k_{cat}=v_{\max}/[E]$. ^d Catalytic efficiency, calculated by k_{cat}/K_M . ^e For L2, K_i cannot be
 342 determined directly from the usual Dixon plot, "K_i" is a more complex function which varies with [I] (K_i^{slope}). *+§ There
 343 are no statistically significant differences for p < 0.05.

344

345 It is noticeable that the compounds M1 and M2, both similar in their structure, perform
 346 a similar inhibition over PPO with no statistical differences between them. The Michaelis
 347 Menten constant maintain the values of the control yet the v_{\max} drops off as the amount
 348 of inhibitor increases in the solution. This behaviour indicates that both ligand M1 and
 349 M2 acts as non-competitive inhibitors. Besides, it seems that the presence of the
 350 pyridine in the structure of M2 does not offer additional inhibitory capability to the

351 ligand. It was also calculated the inhibition constant (k_i) and the IC_{50} for both M1 and M2
352 ligands being about 0.25 mM in both cases. In the case of non-competitive inhibition K_i
353 and IC_{50} parameters must be equal or almost identical, as it is in the case of M1 and M2.
354 Both ligands behave almost identical as there is almost no differences between their
355 constants.

356 In comparison with M1 and M2, M3 offers an extra inhibition power and also a change
357 in the interaction on the PPO. It seems that the increase in the ring size and the extra
358 nitrogen in its structure improve the inhibitory activity of the PPO. In this case, it was
359 necessary to decrease the concentration to 0.33 mM to obtain the same v_{max} as M1 and
360 M2 with a double concentration (0.66 mM). Furthermore, K_m also drops off with a
361 significant difference from the control meaning that the inhibition would be mixed type
362 in contrast to M1 and M2.

363 Next ligand with more inhibition power was L3, which has a 24-membered macrocycle
364 ring, ten nitrogens in total and two naphtha-2-ylmethyl units in its structure. With a
365 concentration of 0.1 mM the maximum rate of the tyrosinase decreases approximately
366 to 0.03 mM min^{-1} , also decreasing in a substantial way the catalytic constant and the
367 catalytic efficiency. Thus, L3 is four times more active than M3 and thirteen times more
368 active than M2 and M1. It supports that when increasing the macrocycle size and the
369 number of nitrogens in the macrocycle, together with the presence of the naphth-2-
370 ylmethyl units, the inhibition power rises as deduced from the PLS analysis.

371 Lastly, L2 has also two naphth-2-ylmethyl units but in contrast with L3, they are directly
372 attached to the ring removing two NH units. This ligand is the most powerful inhibitor
373 of the ten tested ligands. The values of K_M and v_{max} were calculated for three different
374 concentrations of L2 (see table 2 and figure 5a). In all the cases a value of K_M around 1.0

375 mM of substrate was obtained, with no statistically significant differences for $p < 0.05$ in
376 any case. However, the value of v_{\max} decreases from 0.29 to 0.038 mM min^{-1} when
377 increasing the concentration of L2 in the medium. K_M does not vary with the
378 concentration of inhibitor but v_{\max} decreases. Thus, we can conclude that L2 induces a
379 non-competitive inhibition over the PPO enzyme where there is no coordination with
380 the active centre. The catalytic efficiency (k_{cat}/K_M) and the turnover number (k_{cat}) follow
381 the same trend as the v_{\max} , with values close to 1400 mM min^{-1} in absence of the
382 inhibitor that dropped off up to 150 mM min^{-1} indicating that the efficiency of the
383 enzyme is much lower in the presence of L2 at 0.04 mM, the lowest concentration of all
384 the compounds. Furthermore, the IC_{50} parameter was also estimated at $10 \pm 2 \mu\text{M}$ ($n=3$)
385 statistically equal to kojic acid in the same conditions.

386 This result indicates that, in general, the interaction of the compounds with the enzyme
387 is not carried out in the active centre, only M3 presents a mixed type inhibition. This
388 absence of direct interaction could be explained since copper is found in the active site
389 of the enzyme, within a biological structure with a complex quaternary structure and
390 not as a free ion. Although the interaction of the inhibitor with the enzyme is not carried
391 out in the active centre, it is likely to modify the interaction of the substrate with the
392 active centre, avoiding or delaying the formation of products of the reaction ⁴¹

394 Figure 5: A) Lineweaver-Burk plot of dopamine oxidation in presence and absence of
 395 L2. The concentrations of L2 are (■) 0 μM , (●) 5 μM (◆) 10 μM and (▲) 40 μM . B)
 396 Secondary replot of Slope (K_m/V_{max}) vs. [L2]. C) Secondary replot of intercept ($1/V_{\text{max}}$) vs
 397 [L2]). Data of B) and C) are obtained from A).

398

399 3.4. Analysis of L2-mushroom tyrosinase interaction

400 The influence of the inhibitor in the enzymatic activity was analysed through the
 401 study of the variation of the slope and the intercept values with the concentration

402 of L2. In case of conventional Michaelis-Menten systems a linear relationship is
 403 found. As can be seen in the figures 5b and 5c, both the slope (K_M/V_{max}) and the
 404 intercept ($1/V_{max}$) vs [L2] show an excellent fitting to parabolic (R^2 in both cases is
 405 0.999) instead of linear functions. This indicates that the mechanism is rather an
 406 S-parabolic I-parabolic inhibition⁴² where there is either a complex non-
 407 competitive inhibition with multiple inhibitor sites for one enzyme or complex
 408 conformational changes^{43,44}. In these cases, K_i cannot be determined directly from
 409 the usual plots like Dixon, however, a “ K_i ” as a more complex function which
 410 varies with $[I]$ ^{45,46}, was determined from equation (2) where K_i is K_i^{slope} .

$$411 \text{ Slope} = K_M/V_{max} (1+[I]/K_i)^2 \quad (2)$$

412 Applying the equation (1), the K_i^{slope} calculated is $15 \pm 3 \mu\text{M}$.

413 Fluorescence studies were also performed in order to get more insight into the
 414 nature of the enzyme-inhibitor interactions. It was observed that the intensity of
 415 the fluorescence decreases progressively when increasing the amount of L2,
 416 although without any α -significant shift in the maximum intensity. The Stern-
 417 Volmer equation was applied to calculate the Stern-Volmer quenching constant
 418 (K_{sv}) and the k_q (bimolecular quenching rate constant) determining whether the
 419 mechanism was static or dynamic⁴⁷. The corresponding value for K_{sv} is 7.8×10^4
 420 M^{-1} and $7.8 \times 10^{12} \text{M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ for k_q . Assuming that the collision quenching constant of
 421 biomolecules is about $2.0 \times 10^{10} \text{M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$, our k_q is two order of magnitude higher,
 422 suggesting that the inhibition process provoked for L2 shows a static nature with
 423 a binding between the enzyme and the inhibitor⁴⁸. In this case, the number of
 424 binding sites can be obtained by the equation 3^{46,49}:

$$425 \frac{F_0}{F_0-F} = \frac{1}{n} + \frac{1}{K} \frac{1}{[L1]} \quad (3)$$

426 Where F_0 and F are the relative fluorescence intensities of the enzyme with and
427 without the inhibitor respectively, $[L2]$ is the concentration of L2, K is the binding
428 constant and n is the number of binding sites. A good correlation was obtained
429 ($R^2=0.999$) and a value close to 1 ($n = 0.860 \pm 0.005$) was calculated, which
430 indicates the binding of one molecule of L2 to each tyrosinase is enough to change
431 the conformation of the enzyme lowering its activity. Besides a high binding
432 constant was obtained ($(1.869 \pm 0.018) \times 10^5 \text{ M}^{-1}$) in agreement with the great
433 affinity between the enzyme and the inhibitor.

434 3.5. Inhibitory assays on apple juices as real matrices

435 Encouraged by the good results offered by L2 as inhibitor of tyrosinase in model
436 systems, its performance was checked in a real food system as it is the case of a
437 freshly obtained apple juice. For that purpose, apples of the c.v. Golden Delicious
438 variety were liquefied and put in contact with two different concentrations (0.5
439 mM and 1.5 mM) of L2, afterward, the samples were left stirring for one hour. In
440 general terms, once the apples liquefies, the enzymatic browning process begins
441 quickly. The colour change is perceptible to the human eye within the first 5-10
442 minutes. As we can see in the figure 6a, in absence of inhibitor the juice suffers a
443 strong oxidation of the polyphenols even in the first 10 minutes, changing from
444 bright yellow to an orange colour that becomes reddish after 30 minutes and
445 reaches almost a full oxidative browning after 1 hour.

446 When the juice is put in contact with the lowest concentration of L2 (0.5 mM) the
 447 enzymatic browning is delayed during the first 10 minutes, however, the reaction
 448 is not completely stopped and the colour of the juice reaches a browning intensity
 449 similar to that observed in the absence of inhibitor at longer times (60 minutes)).
 450 Raising the concentration of L2 in the juice to 1.5 mM, the inhibiting effect of the
 451 azamacrocyclic ligand was strong enough to stop the process. The colour change
 452 of the juice mixed with the 1.5 mM of L2 is almost inappreciable during the first
 453 30 minutes darkening slightly after 60 minutes.

454
 455 Figure 6: A) Colour evolution in apple juice without the inhibitor (left) and in the
 456 presence of 1.5 mM of L2 (right). B) Measurements of colour difference ΔE over time:
 457 control (grey) and with 1.5 mM L2 (striped).

458
 459 Figure 6b collects the colour change differences (ΔE_{ab}^*) for the apple juice in
 460 presence and absence of inhibitor, taking the freshly prepared juice as reference.
 461 In agreement with the naked eye colour changes, it can be noticed how after the
 462 first 10 minutes the control reaches an ΔE_{ab}^* close to 20 which continues

463 growing, while the one with inhibitor barely has an ΔE_{ab}^* of 5 that is maintained
464 during the 30 minutes. At longer times (1 hour) the control shows a colour similar
465 to the 30 minutes indicating that the oxidation is almost complete. However, the
466 sample containing L2 (1.5 mM) holds a significant reduction in the enzymatic
467 browning, although a slight increase in the ΔE_{ab}^* is observed suggesting that a
468 residual activity is maintained at long times.

469 In conclusion, during the present study the influence over the enzymatic
470 browning of ten azamacrocyclic ligands with diverse functionalisation has been
471 tested showing that they can be potentially used as inhibitory products of PPO to
472 a greater or lesser extent. Their chemical structures strongly influence the
473 inhibitory activity being the ring size and the number of nitrogens in the
474 macrocycle (both correlated) the main factor. Also, the presence of bulky
475 aromatic groups attached to the macrocycle was relevant. The inhibition of the
476 enzymatic browning is mainly due to the deactivation of the PPO and suffers a
477 significant rise if the contact time between the enzyme the ligand increases. For
478 L2, the most active inhibitor, kinetic studies indicate that ligands interact with the
479 tyrosinase enzyme with a non-competitive mechanism in a molar proportion of
480 1:1 giving rise to structural change on the protein that provokes an abrupt
481 decrease in its activity. The high inhibitory activity of L2 was verified on a real
482 sample showing how it can reduce the enzymatic browning in an apple juice when
483 used at 1.5 mM. L2 opens the door to a new strategy based on systems that
484 conjugate polyamines and aromatic groups as tyrosinase inhibitors.

485

486

487 **Acknowledgments**

488 Financial support by the Spanish Ministerio de Ciencia, Innovación y
489 Universidades (project RTI2018-100910-B-C44), Ministerio de Economía y
490 Competitividad (projects CTQ2016-78499-C6-1-R, Unidad de Excelencia MDM
491 2015-0038 and CTQ2017-90852-REDC) and Generalitat Valenciana (Project
492 PROMETEOII2015-002) is gratefully acknowledged.

493

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649 **Table of contents**

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A novel naphthalene derivatized azamacrocycle performs a S-parabolic I-parabolic non-competitive inhibition over tyrosinase enzyme in the micromolar range.

